

Effect of selected Asanas in Hatha Yoga on peak expiratory flow rate and vital capacity among intercollege yoginis

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Abstract. The purpose of this study was to find out the effects of selected yoga asanas on peak expiratory flow rate and vital capacity. The subjects for the present were selected on the basis of random group design. Thirty (N=30) inter-college yoginis were selected as subject for the present study from D.A.V. Institute of Engineering & Technology, Jalandhar, Punjab, INDIA. All subjects ranged between the chronological age of 18-24. The selected subjects were further divided into two groups. Experimental treatment was then assigned to group "A" and group "B" acts as control. The subjects were subjected to a six week yoga asana training programme which included Eka Pada Sirsasana, Purna Bhujangasana, Dhanur Asana, Gomukh Asana, Chakra Asana, and Vaktayan Asana. The difference in the mean of each group for selected variable was tested for the significance of difference by "t" test. The level of significance was set at 0.05. The results have shown a significant improvement in peak expiratory flow rate, since cal. $t (=6.985) > \text{tab } t .05 (14) (=2.145)$. The treatment of six week yoga asana training programme also showed significant improvement in case of vital capacity, since cal. $t (=12.558) > \text{tab } t .05 (14) (=2.145)$.

Keywords: *Hatha Yoga, peak expiratory flow rate, vital capacity.*

Introduction

The civilization of India has produced a great variety of systems of spiritual beliefs and practices. Ancient seers used yoga as a means to explore the exterior and interior world and, perhaps, ultimately to achieve wisdom and knowledge of the sacred Indian texts: the Vedas, Upanishads and Shastras.

Yoga has been practiced in India for thousands of years, and is traditionally used by spiritual seekers as a system of self-development for purification of the body and mind (G. Feuerstein, 2001). Yoga is proposed to be a preventive as well as curative system for the body, mind and spirit.

The Sanskrit word "yoga" comes from the root *yug* (to join), or yoke (to bind together or to concentrate). Essentially, however, the word "yoga" has come to describe a means of uniting or a method of discipline: to join the body to the mind and together join to the self (soul), or the union between the individual self and the transcendental self. Ayurvedic texts describe 8 components or arms of Yoga that encompass a

philosophy of life: (1) yama (self-restraint); (2) niyama (routines); (3) asana (postures and physical exercises); (4) pranayama (use of breathing to achieve focus); (5) pratyahara (withdrawal of mind from sense organs); (6) dharana (concentration); (7) dhyana (meditation); and (8) samadhi (emancipation). Asana and pranayama have been incorporated alongside Ayurvedic medicine as the basis of a system of medical therapy.

Exercising postures or Asanas in Hatha Yoga has two essential objectives. The first is that to practice any real meditation, one needs at the least one posture in which one can be perfectly comfortable for a longer period of time. The more such postures one can master, the better the basis for developing the inner meditation techniques. The second objective of exercising asanas in Hatha Yoga is to bring health and energy to body and mind by opening the nadis. The practice of Hatha Yoga can help you recognize your hidden physical and mental potentials.

Through the continued performance of Asanas, you will gain flexibility and strength, and learn to be more relaxed under otherwise stressful situations. Hatha yoga is the physical part of yoga practice and is beneficial to the body both mentally and physically. It creates a balance in our physical and mental states. It reduces stress, rejuvenates us and improves circulation and as a result this study was undertaken to find out the effects of selected yoga asanas on peak expiratory flow rate and vital capacity.

Methods

Selection of subjects. The subjects for the present were selected on the basis of random group design. Thirty (N=30) yoginis were selected as subject for the present study from D.A.V. Institute of Engineering and Technology, Jalandhar (Punjab), INDIA who had represented Punjab Technical University in Yoga Championship. All subjects ranged between the chronological age of 18-25 years. The selected subjects were further divided into two groups. Experimental treatment was then assigned to group "A" and group "B" acts as control. The subjects were subjected to a six week yoga asana training programme which included Eka Pada Sirsasana, Purna Bhujangasana, Dhanur Asana, Gomukh Asana, Chakra Asana, and Vaktayan Asana. To find out the effect of selected asanas on peak expiratory flow rate and vital capacity among intercollege yoginis, the following variables were selected for the study: Vital capacity; Peak Expiratory Flow Rate.

Test administration

The vital capacity (VC) is the volume, measured at the mouth, between the position of full inspiration and expiration. It is the total amount of air that an individual can breathe in and out of their lungs in a single maximum breath. Vital capacity was measured by a spirometer. Spirometer was calibrated to record the true volume of air exhaled into or through them. The accuracy of this calibration was checked with a calibration syringe to ensure that the spirometer continues to record volumes accurately. The subject was made to sit and breathe normally through the mouthpiece of spirometer. It was made sure the nose clips are on. Subjects filled their lung as much as possible. As soon as they had their lungs fully inflated, they blew all the air out as fast as they could. Then mouthpieces were removed. Nose clips were taken off.

The best of 3 Forced Vital Capacity (FVC) manoeuvres were taken, the best 2 being within 5% of each other.

Expiratory peak flow (PEF) is the maximum flow generated during expiration performed with maximal force and started after a full inspiration. The subject was made to stand up and it was ensured that the indicator is at the bottom of the meter (zero). The subject was then asked to take a deep breath in, filling the lungs completely and place the mouthpiece in the mouth; lightly bite with the teeth and close the lips on it. The subject was asked to keep the tongue away from the mouthpiece and blast the air out as hard and as fast as possible in a single blow. The best of three readings is used as the recorded value of the peak expiratory flow rate.

Six weeks of Yoga Sanas training programme. The students went through yogic exercises (for six week) through training programme under strict supervision of the researcher. Experimental group practiced following asana during the training:

1. Eka Pada Sirsasana; 2. Purna Bhujangasana;
3. Dhanur Asana; 4. Gomukh Asana; 5. Chakra Asana; 6. Vaktayan Asana.

Findings and results

The study was conducted to find out the effects of selected asanas on peak expiratory flow rate and vital capacity among intercollegiate yoginis. The statistical analysis of data collected on thirty (N=30) subjects. For each of the chosen variable, the results pertaining to significant difference, if any, between experimental and control groups were assessed by "t" test and are presented in following tables.

Table 3 shows that the mean of vital capacity of pre-test of experimental group and post-test of experimental group was 3.333 and 4.3867 respectively, whereas the mean of vital capacity of pre-test of control and post-test of control group was 3.4800 and 3.5400. The "t" value in case of experimental group was 12.558 and for control group it was 0.438. Since $\text{cal. } t (=12.558) > \text{tab } t .05 (14) (=2.145)$, H_0 (null hypothesis) is rejected at .05 level of significance. Thus it may be concluded that six week training program of selected asanas by intercollege yoginis showed significant improvement in vital capacity. As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence. The graphical representation of responses has been exhibited in figure1.

Table 1. VITAL CAPACITY OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	3.3333	4.3867
95% CI for the mean	2.9668 to 3.6999	4.1013 to 4.6720
Variance	0.4381	0.2655
Standard deviation	0.6619	0.5153
Standard error of the mean	0.1709	0.1330

Paired samples t-test

Mean difference	1.0533
Standard deviation	0.3248
95% CI	0.8734 to 1.2332
Test statistic t	12.558
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	14
Two-tailed probability	P<0.0001

Table 2. VITAL CAPACITY OF CONTROL GROUP

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	3.4800	3.5400
95% CI for the mean	3.1563 to 3.8037	3.3507 to 3.7293
Variance	0.3417	0.1169
Standard deviation	0.5846	0.3418
Standard error of the mean	0.1509	0.0883

Paired samples t-test

Mean difference	0.0600
Standard deviation	0.5302
95% CI	-0.23336 to 0.3536
Test statistic t	0.438
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	14
Two-tailed probability	P=0.6679

Table 3. MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION (SD), STANDARD ERROR OF MEAN (SEM) OF VITAL CAPACITY OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP

Group	Number	Mean	S.D.	SEM	't' Value	
Experimental (Pre-test)	15	3.3333	0.6619	0.1709	12.558	
Experimental (Post-test)	15	4.3867	0.5153	0.1330		
Control (Pre-test)	15	3.4800	0.5846	0.1509		
Control (Post-test)	15	3.5400	0.3418	0.0883		
						0.438

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence. "t" .05 (14) = 2.145

Figure 1. MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION (SD), STANDARD ERROR OF MEAN (SEM) OF VITALCAPACITY OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP

Figure 2. P-VALUE, TWO TAILED AND ONE TAILED PROBABILITY VALUES OF A T-TEST OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP OF VITAL CAPACITY

Figure 3. P-VALUE, TWO TAILED AND ONE TAILED PROBABILITY VALUES OF A T-TEST OF CONTROL GROUP OF VITAL CAPACITY

Table 4. PEAK EXPIRATORY FLOW RATE OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	615.6667	668.6667
95% CI for the mean	587.2678 to 644.0755	630.2501 to 707.0832
Variance	2631.6667	4812.3810
Standard deviation	51.2998	69.3713
Standard error of the mean	13.2455	17.9116

Paired samples t-test

Mean difference	53.0000
Standard deviation	29.3866
95% CI	36.7263 to 69.2737
Test statistic t	6.985
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	14
Two-tailed probability	P<0.0001

Table 5. PEAK EXPIRATORY FLOW RATE OF CONTROL GROUP

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	621.3333	625.6667
95% CI for the mean	594.1539 to 648.5127	590.0092 to 661.3241
Variance	2408.8095	4145.9524
Standard deviation	49.0796	64.3891
Standard error of the mean	12.6723	16.6252

Paired samples t-test

Mean difference	4.3333
Standard deviation	26.5832
95% CI	-10.3880 to 19.05446
Test statistic t	0.631
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	14
Two-tailed probability	P=0.5380

Table 6. MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION (SD), STANDARD ERROR OF MEAN (SEM) OF PEAK EXPIRATORY FLOW RATE VOLUME OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP

Group	Number	Mean	S.D.	SEM	't' Value
Experimental (Pre-test)	15	615.6667	51.2998	13.2455	6.985 0.631
Experimental (Post-test)	15	668.6667	69.3713	17.9116	
Control (Pre-test)	15	621.3333	49.0796	12.6723	
Control (Post-test)	15	625.6667	64.3891	16.6252	

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence. "t" .05 (14) = 2.145

Table 6 shows that the mean of peak expiratory flow rate of pre-test of experimental group and post-test of experimental group was 615.6667 and 668.6667 respectively, whereas the mean of peak expiratory flow rate of pre-test of control and post-test of control group was 621.3333 and 625.6667. The "t" value in case of experimental group was 6.985 and for control group it was 0.631.

Since cal. t (=6.985) > tab t .05 (14) (=2.145), Ho (null hypothesis) is rejected at .05 level of significance. Thus it may be concluded that six week training program of selected asanas by intercollege yoginis leads to significant improvement in peak expiratory flow rate. As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence. The graphical representation of responses has been exhibited in figure 4.

Figure 4. MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION (SD), STANDARD ERROR OF MEAN (SEM) OF MAXIMAL VENTILATORY VOLUME OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP

Figure 5. P-VALUE, TWO TAILED AND ONE TAILED PROBABILITY VALUES OF A t-TEST OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP OF PEAK EXPIRATORY FLOW RATE

Figure 6. P-VALUE, TWO TAILED AND ONE TAILED PROBABILITY VALUES OF A t-TEST OF CONTROL GROUP OF PEAK EXPIRATORY FLOW RATE

STATISTICAL PROCEDURE USED. The random group design was used for the study. Two groups were made of the subjects each comprising of 15 subjects. The difference in the mean of each group for selected variable was tested for the significance of difference by “t” test. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Hypothesis: $H_0: \mu_y = \mu_x$; $H_1: \mu_y \geq \mu_x$

Level of significance: 0.05

Inference: Since calculated “t” is greater than tab t.05, H_0 (null hypothesis) may be rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus it may be concluded that six week training program of selected asanas to intercollege yoginis leads to significant improvement in vital capacity and peak expiratory flow rate. As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence.

Discussion

From the results it is evident that the six week yoga asana training programme which included Eka Pada Sirsasana, Poorna Bhujangasana, Dhanur Asana, Gomukh Asana, Chakra Asana, and Vaktayan Asana had shown a significant improvement in vital capacity. The findings are supported by the study conducted by Birkel DA, Edgren L. on “Hatha Yoga: Improved vital capacity of students” to determine the effects of yoga postures and breathing exercises on vital capacity showed a statistically significant ($P < .001$) improvement in vital capacity across all categories over time. Whereas the results have also shown significant improvement in Peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR) and the findings are supported by the study conducted by Nagendra H.R. & Nagarathna R. on “An integrated Approach of Yoga Therapy for Bronchial Asthma: A 3 -54-Month Prospective Study” which showed a statistically significant ($p < .005$) improvement in Peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR) across the complete group.

Conclusion

Findings of this exploratory study suggest that the treatment of six week yoga asana training programme which included Eka Pada Sirsasana, Poorna Bhujangasana, Dhanur Asana, Gomukh Asana, Chakra Asana, and Vaktayan Asana showed significant improvement in peak expiratory flow rate and vital capacity.

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